

Getting a grip on jackals: Net-gunning as an efficient and cost-effective approach to capturing Black-backed jackals (*Canidae: Lupulella mesomelas*)

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ABSTRACT

Wildlife research and management often depend on safe and efficient capture methods. The inability to effectively capture elusive species can limit research and inhibit the ability to make informed management recommendations. Therefore, adapting established capture techniques to novel species and environments is essential in wildlife conservation. The Black-backed jackal *Lupulella mesomelas* is associated with substantial stock losses throughout southern Africa. Furthermore, this is a species that is both elusive and difficult to capture alive, especially in areas where they have been persecuted. Despite its notoriety as a damage-causing animal, data on this species are relatively sparse, primarily due to researchers' inability to capture a meaningful number of animals as a research sample. Helicopter net-gunning has been a successful tool for capturing several species of canids worldwide, but there are no practical records of its viability or utility for capturing Black-backed jackals. We attempted to capture jackals using helicopter-based net-gunning in a small stock farming area in South Africa. Our single-day pilot study in the southern Free State located four jackals and resulted in one capture. The more extensive primary investigation in the Eastern Cape located 20 animals of which 12 were captured. We compared capture efficacy and cost per unit animal using net-gunning to a padded leghold approach for the same area. Capture time per individual and time to catch the target study sample was lower than that for leghold trapping. The cost per unit animal was also lower compared to leghold trapping. Furthermore, under our study circumstances net-gunning was more cost effective and the study animals were subjected to restraint and the associated stress for a relatively shorter time than during leghold trapping. Therefore, net-gunning may be beneficial where synchrony of data collection for multiple jackals is important.

KEYWORDS: Black-backed jackal, *Lupulella mesomelas*, mesopredator, helicopter net-gunning, wildlife capture

INTRODUCTION

The Black-backed jackal *Lupulella mesomelas* (hereafter jackal) are medium-sized canids widely distributed throughout southern and eastern Africa. They are highly adaptable generalist omnivores that thrive in natural and anthropogenically modified habitats (Minnie *et al.* 2018). They are also considered damage-causing mesopredators, with a considerable negative impact on livestock production in South Africa (Van Niekerk 2010; Spies 2011; Bergman *et al.* 2013; Turpie & Babatopie 2018). Unfortunately, most studies of jackal ecology have been confined to nature reserves; however, recently, there seems to be an increased interest in their ecology in farmland ecosystems (Du Plessis *et al.* 2015; Avenant *et al.*, in prep., this volume).

Jackals are notoriously difficult to capture alive, particularly on farmlands where they are persecuted, and are highly adaptive to capture methods (Minnie *et al.* 2016; Natrass *et al.* 2020). The elusive nature

of jackals is highlighted by the low capture rates achieved in various studies. Kaunda (2001; South-eastern Botswana, foothold trap) and Rowe-Rowe & Green (1981; KwaZulu-Natal, foothold trap) achieved capture rates of only 1.5 jackals per 100 trap nights. Botha *et al.* (2022; Free State, Western Cape and Gauteng, foothold trap) reported a higher rate of 14.6 jackals per 100 trap nights in protected areas, slightly lower than 16.7 jackals per 100 trap nights recorded by Loveridge and Macdonald (2001; Zimbabwe, foothold trap), also in a protected area. On farmlands the capture success is considerably lower, as Drouilly (2019) and Botha *et al.* (2022) achieved the rate of 0.6 jackals per 100 trap nights using foothold traps in the Western Cape. In addition, the animals that were captured comprised primarily young individuals; older canids are known to exhibit heightened territorial awareness and caution compared to the young (Sequin *et al.* 2003; Avenant & Du Plessis 2008), particularly in response to an increase in human presence (Brand & Nel 1997; Kaunda 2001). In contrast, younger animals are

more prone to wandering over larger areas before establishing territories (Gese *et al.* 1987; Sequin *et al.* 2003), potentially resulting in a higher capture rate of transients.

The low capture rates of jackals represent a significant impediment for researchers seeking to conduct ecological and/or management-related studies. A failure to capture a sufficiently large sample within the limited timeframes usually associated with research projects hinders the collection of adequate data for the robust population-level analysis. Low sample sizes limit the scope and accuracy of the research, ultimately reducing the inferential frame relative to the eco-systematics and management. Developing a more effective method of capturing jackals than the traditional trapping will benefit not only research, but also future management of this species.

Devices commonly used to capture jackals for research include cage traps and padded leghold traps (Craft 2007; Kamler *et al.* 2008; Du Plessis *et al.* 2018). There are advantages and disadvantages associated with both techniques (Pawlina & Proulx 1999; Du Plessis *et al.* 2018). These traps are indiscriminate, and bycatch of non-target animals can result in injuries (Michalski *et al.* 2007). These techniques are non-selective in relation to specific cohorts within a population. Canid social structure can influence capture rates due to the variation of behaviour expressed in individuals' social roles (Harris & Knowlton 2001). Behavioural differences may lead to sexually and ontogenetically biased trapping results (Kay *et al.* 2000). The deployment and management of cage and leghold traps may be adversely affected by rugged terrain and is also time-consuming and may require the participation of multiple researchers.

Cage traps are a relatively inexpensive but labour-intensive method (Way *et al.* 2002; Du Plessis *et al.* 2018). However, jackals are cautious predators and are rarely captured efficiently using these devices (Kaunda 2001; Loveridge & Macdonald 2001; Humphries *et al.* 2016; PMF 2016). Similarly low capture rates using cage traps have been demonstrated in other canids, such as foxes *Vulpes vulpes* (Mierzejewska *et al.* 2020) and coyotes *Canis latrans* (Way *et al.* 2002). Capture rates in areas with high anthropogenic activity are further reduced as compensatory behaviours develop (Sequin *et al.* 2003; Avenant & Du Plessis 2008). Growing

wariness formed through learned behaviour may bias the capture demographic, leading to an increase in relatively inexperienced younger individuals being trapped (Botha *et al.* 2022). The caution exhibited by older jackals is likely a behavioural adaptation to prolonged lethal control measures on farmlands (Botha *et al.* 2022). While captive in cage traps, jackals can incur injuries and experience elevated levels of stress (Way *et al.* 2002; Powell & Proulx 2003). The effectiveness of cage trapping is influenced by a range of factors including the location, habitat, resource availability, and land-use and management practices (Powell & Proulx 2003). The time of year may also have an impact on captures as it may be easier to trap inexperienced young individuals, especially during the early part of the dispersing season.

Leghold traps, equipped with off-set rubber-padded jaws, are typically more effective at capturing canids (Padilla & Hilton 2015; PMF 2016; Du Plessis *et al.* 2018). Such padded leghold devices are relatively inexpensive and have a demonstrated efficacy for jackal capture (Kamler *et al.* 2008; PMF 2016), although they require substantial effort to monitor and maintain (daily checking and rebaiting where necessary; Du Plessis *et al.* 2018). Animals with large home ranges or occurring in low densities may necessitate multiple trap lines, requiring additional personnel for their effective monitoring and management. While deemed safe under most circumstances, leghold traps can cause injuries to both target and non-target species (Onderka *et al.* 1990; Phillips *et al.* 1996; Du Plessis *et al.* 2018). They are unselective, but triggers can be tensioned to exclude smaller, non-target species (Kamler *et al.* 2002; PMF 2016). However, heavier, non-target animals can trigger traps and experience severe injuries. Furthermore, predators may target animals trapped in leghold devices as easy prey (McKenzie 1990). Leghold traps are often heavily regulated and require specialist training (PMF 2016), with their use being completely banned in some regions (e.g. United Kingdom, Council Regulation (EEC) No 3254/91¹). Therefore, the viability of alternative methods, such as aerial net-gunning, needs to be explored.

The practice of using a net fired from a helicopter to capture wild animals, known as helicopter net-gunning, was first developed in New Zealand for the capture of red deer *Cervus elaphus* during the 1970s (Yerex 2001). Helicopter net-gunning has been a valuable tool for capturing canid species, such as

coyotes *Canis latrans* and wolves *Canis lupus* in North America (Nelson *et al.* 2006; Latham *et al.* 2013). Net-gunning allows efficient, representative, and targeted animal capture in a variety of habitats (Barret *et al.* 1982). Although net-gunning from a helicopter can be expensive, researchers often employ this method as it provides several advantages over other standardised trapping and capture techniques. Using net-gunning, researchers can, for instance, capture multiple animals quickly over a large area (Webb *et al.* 2008). Another advantage is realised by eliminating the bycatch associated with other methods (Kamler *et al.* 2000). Although not necessitated by our study, net-gunning could target specific cohorts based on morphologically distinguishable features such as size, colour and sex, which may be important depending on the research focus (Benz *et al.* 2016). Despite the advantages of net-gunning, there are risks to the target animals, including, but not limited to, mortalities, morbidities and traumatic injuries (Webb *et al.* 2008; Van de Kerk *et al.* 2020). Mortality and serious injury rates for helicopter net-gunning of canids are, however, generally low (Nelson *et al.* 2006).

During a study of the ecology of jackals on a small stock farming area in the Eastern Cape, a practical method was required to capture and collar jackals. A pilot project to establish the feasibility of aerial net-gunning was implemented in the southern Free State within a matrix of predominantly small livestock and game farms (Green *et al.* 2021). The investigation was subsequently transferred to the northern part of the Eastern Cape, where further helicopter net-gunning was conducted. This study introduces the first recorded use of a helicopter-based net-gun capture approach of jackals for research purposes. We assess the utility of this approach for jackals both in terms of efficacy and cost effectiveness relative to leghold trapping. Furthermore, we comment on negative impacts (such as the frequency of injuries and deaths) that relate to the use of this capture technique.

METHODS

Study area

Both the southern Free State (30°30'S 26°07'E) and Eastern Cape (31°29'S 26°03'E) study areas comprise a heterogeneous, undulating landscape. The pilot study in the southern Free State and the Eastern Cape study areas fall within, or are close to, the overlap of

the Grassland and Nama Karoo biomes and contain aspects of both (Mucina *et al.* 2006). Both areas are topographically similar, comprising rocky outcrops and valleys where wildlife and local agriculture are supported by ephemeral streams and groundwater aquifers (Fig. 1).

The Free State site has two distinct vegetation regions, viz., open grasslands that span the “steppe” (Xhariep Karroid Grassland) and thick shrubland covers the slopes and valleys (Besemkaree Koppies Shrubland) (Mucina *et al.* 2006) (Fig. 2). The altitude ranges from 1200–1600 m above sea level. The climate is cold and semi-arid, with the dry season from May to November, and the wet summer rainfall season extending from December to April (SAWS²).

The Eastern Cape site has three distinct vegetation regions, with a dynamic mixture of grassland and shrubland spanning the study area (Eastern Upper Karoo, NKu4; Mucina *et al.* 2006), thick shrubland covers the slopes and valleys (Tarkastad Montane Shrubland, Gs17; Mucina *et al.* 2006), and open grassland dominates the eastern plateau (Karoo Escarpment Grassland, Gh1; Mucina *et al.* 2006) (Fig. 3). The altitude ranges from 1300–1900 m above sea level. The dry season is from May to November, and the wet summer rainfall season extends from December to April (SAWS¹).

Capture protocols

The pilot investigation in the Free State, near Bethulie, was carried out in August 2019 and was limited to a single day with four hours of flight time (two two-hour flight sessions: 08h00–10h00 and 15h00–17h00). Subsequent captures were undertaken near the town of Steynsburg in the Eastern Cape, in August 2020, February 2021 and October 2021. Here each capture session consisted of approximately six hours of flight time spread across two to three days. However, additional attempts were made on an *ad hoc* basis, coinciding with the landowner's game management practices. Helicopter net-gunning was implemented using a contracted team consisting of a helicopter pilot and a net-gunner, and a veterinarian on the ground. Capture attempts were conducted during the cooler times of the day (early in the morning and late in the afternoon) to reduce heat stress on the target animals and coincide with anticipated activity peaks of jackals (Kaunda 2000).

Figure 1: Location of the study areas approximately 20 km north of Bethulie in the southern Free State and approximately 30 km south-east of Steynsburg in the Eastern Cape, South Africa. The distance between the two study areas is approximately 140 km.

Areas targeted for capture attempts were selected based on prior reconnaissance using a combination of spoor tracking, camera traps and local knowledge. Transects were then flown within the target areas at an altitude of 20–30 m above ground. A siren on the helicopter was sounded intermittently to flush jackals. Once a jackal was located, the helicopter chased the jackal into an open area that was suitable for a capture attempt. Jackals were then captured using a net (3×3 m, 8 cm mesh diameter, pre-loaded within a canister that was attached to the net gun), weighted with four 800 g cylinders, and fired from a 0.308 calibre, breakaway net-gun (CODA Net Gun³). The chase time was strictly limited to ≤ 10 min for each animal to moderate stress and lower the chance of capture myopathy (Bartsch *et al.* 1977). Spare, pre-loaded net canisters were carried in the helicopter so that they could be rapidly loaded onto the gun if the initial shot was missed.

Following the successful netting of a jackal, the helicopter was safely landed in the vicinity of the

netted animal (as close as possible to but as far as necessary from the jackal) to minimise the time it would take the net-gunner to get to the animal to minimise stress and to prevent the animal from escaping. The netted jackal was approached on foot, and the first person to arrive immobilised the head by securely holding it to the ground using a rubber pole. A small, lightweight blanket was placed over the animal's head and the muzzle was restrained, leaving the nostrils free to allow unimpeded breathing. Subsequently, the animal, still entangled in the net, was carefully transferred into a capture/transport bag and transported by helicopter to the tagging team. To minimise the risk of harm to either the jackal or the aircrew, the capture bag was designed to allow the jackal to breathe while preventing the animal from biting through the bag and injuring occupants of the helicopter. The top of the bag was clamped down for additional protection. Throughout the journey the net-gunner, wearing thick protective gloves, maintained a secure hold on the bag above the clamp to prevent escape. The duration of the transfer flight

Figure 2: A map outlining the vegetation types according to Mucina *et al.* (2006) for the study area in the southern Free State, South Africa.

from the capture site to the ground team was limited to three minutes. The net-gunner and pilot resumed their search for more jackals immediately after the captured jackal was handed over to the ground team. Once the jackal was removed from the helicopter it was released into a covered recovery cage where the veterinarian monitored it for approximately 30 minutes. The jackal was then anaesthetised using a pole syringe with a mixture of medetomidine (Dormitor, Zoetis, 0.05 mg/kg), ketamine (Anaket, Bayer, 10 mg/kg) and butorphanol (Kyron Laboratories, 0.15 mg/kg). A physical examination was conducted onsite by the attending veterinarian to determine the jackal's body condition and to identify signs of injury or contraindications for collaring. The evaluation also noted morphometrics, age, sex and health indicators (including dehydration, parasitic load, scar tissue, tooth wear and eruption, and disease symptoms). After the initial assessment, the researcher fitted a two-way GPS telemetry/tracking collar with a built-in drop-off function (Followit AB, Lindesberg, Sweden) to the jackal. The collar, weighing 240 g in accordance with the prescribed maximum weight for research

animals (Kenward 2000; Sikes & ACUCASM 2016), featured an integrated mortality sensor programmed to send an alert after 12 hours of inactivity. The jackal was released at the capture site upon the veterinarian's approval, after the reversal antagonist atipamezole (Antisedan, Zoetis, 0.25 mg/kg) had been administered. Contrary to the above protocol, the jackal captured in the Free State was anaesthetised immediately after initial capture with a net-gun.

To facilitate the comparison between the cost and capture success of helicopter net-gunning and padded foothold traps (Victor #3 Softcatch, Lititz, PA), we implemented two focussed leg-hold trapping sessions conducted by a professional trapper on the same sites. These sessions were conducted from 15 May – 10 June 2019 and from 1–21 August 2020. Leghold traps were deployed for a total of 16 consecutive days and nights in the Free State and 15 days and nights in the Eastern Cape. There was a cumulative increase in the daily number of traps deployed in the Free State (range 6–42) and the Eastern Cape (range 6–41). This resulted in a trapping effort, calculated by the

Figure 3: A map outlining the vegetation types according to Mucina *et al.* (2006) for the study area in the Eastern Cape, South Africa.

number of traps multiplied by period of exposure (trap-days), of 498 for the Free State and 388 for the Eastern Cape.

The cost per collared jackal was calculated by dividing the total cost, excluding veterinary fees, by the number of successfully collared jackals for each method. The exchange rate applied for the conversion between the South African Rand (ZAR) and United States Dollar (USD) for international comparison is accepted as 1 USD = 18.84 ZAR (30 October 2023). To assess the efficiency of jackal capture methods, we analysed the success rate of each technique by comparing the number of successful collaring events and the duration of implementation. Regarding the net-gunning approach we only considered the data from when the helicopter was actively searching for jackals for more than an hour. This caveat was implemented as there were several instances of haphazard searching coinciding with landowner's game management practices.

To optimise efficiency and reduce potential harm or stress to the animals, the padded foothold traps were checked twice a day, at sunrise and sunset, and baited

as needed. Upon the capture of a jackal, the animal was anaesthetised and fitted with a GPS telemetry/tracking collar. Subsequently, the jackal was transferred to a recovery cage where it was subject to veterinary monitoring until it had fully recovered from the anaesthesia and then it was released.

All these capture and handling methods were reviewed and approved by the University of South Africa's Animal Research Ethics Committee (application number 2018/CAES/i16).

RESULTS

During the pilot study in the Free State we located four jackals, of which one was captured. Two jackals were sighted sitting next to natural dens or culverts and escaped into them. The third jackal escaped into dense vegetation before a helicopter chase could be initiated. The first three animals were sighted during the two-hour morning flight session. The successfully captured jackal was located within 30 minutes of take-off in the afternoon session and was chased for two minutes and three seconds before being netted. A veterinary examination of this jackal

Table 1. The number of jackals sighted and captured during the helicopter net-gun flying sessions at a small-stock farming region in the Eastern Cape, South Africa, 2020–2021. Each capture session records the number of days flown alongside the number of hours spent in the air. The capture rate for the number of jackals captured per hour is calculated and presented for each day of flying.

Eastern Cape					
Capture session	Day	Flight time (hours)	Number of jackals sighted	Number of jackals captured	Captures / hour
1	1	4	4	2	0.5
	2	2	2	1	0.5
2	1	1	1	0*	0
	2	3	0	0	0
	3	2	3	2	1
3	1	2	0	0	0
	2	2	5	4	2
	3	2	4	2	1
4	1	1	1	1	1
	2	3	0	0	0
Summary	Days spent flying	Total flight time	Total number of jackals sighted	Total number of jackals captured	Overall captures / hour
	10	22	20	12	0.55

*Jackal netted but escaped by chewing through the net

identified no physical injuries, and the animal was successfully released. This resulted in a capture rate of 0.25 jackals per flight hour. During the foothold trapping period in the southern Free State, a single jackal was captured and successfully released with a GPS telemetry/tracking collar, resulting in a capture rate of 0.2 jackals per 100 trap-days.

At the Eastern Cape study site, we located 20 jackals and successfully netted 12 during 22 hours of flight time, resulting in a capture rate of 0.55 jackals per flight hour. Among the 12 captures, two were identified as recaptures. The first recapture was a chance occurrence that resulted in replacing a faulty collar, while the second was a deliberate effort to replace a collar with a low battery. A 13th jackal was also netted but escaped by chewing through the capture net before the crew could get to the animal. Of the eight jackals that eluded capture, six escaped into dens or through natural watercourses, and two fled into a narrow valley that was inaccessible to the helicopter. The chase times for 11 of the 20 individuals sighted by the helicopter were recorded. Five jackals were captured within two minutes of being sighted, while another three jackals were captured after pursuits lasting less than three minutes. Chase times longer than six minutes generally resulted in the jackal escaping (n=3); although, one jackal was successfully captured after a chase of eight minutes. Chase times for individuals that were not captured were not recorded due to jackals escaping prior to the initiation of a chase (chase time was negligible). The

capture success achieved for jackals using net-gunning varied (Table 1). The highest number of jackals captured on a single day was four. During the foothold trapping period in the Eastern Cape, two jackals were captured and fitted with GPS telemetry/tracking collars, resulting in a capture rate of 0.5 jackals per 100 trap-days.

All captured jackals were assessed by an attending veterinarian before release and were found to be in good condition. Only four of the net-gunned jackals received minor injuries, assumed to be associated with their capture: two jackals had minor (<2 cm) cuts on their tongues, one jackal was missing a toenail on the front paw, and one had a minor abrasion on its hind leg. One mortality was recorded during the net-gun capturing: there were no external signs of injury resulting from the capture, but the animal did not recover from sedation despite the administration of the anaesthetic antagonist. For all the individuals (n=3) captured using leghold devices, minor lacerations (≤5 cm) were recorded on the trapped foot. The veterinarian assessed these cuts, none of which required more treatment than administration of the topical wound spray Oxytetracycline (Terramycin wound spray, Zoetis).

Ten of the net-gunned jackals captured were fitted with GPS transmitters (Free State n=1, Eastern Cape n=9). The jackal net-gunned and collared in the Free State died and its carcass was found one day

after the animal was released, approximately 200 m away from where it was freed. The mortality of this jackal was caused by capture myopathy possibly due to an adverse reaction to the anaesthetics and human error (Strauss⁴, pers. comm. 2019). No other mortalities were recorded that could be associated with net-gunning of jackals. Of the individuals captured using the padded leghold traps (Free State $n=1$, Eastern Cape $n=2$), one mortality was recorded in the Eastern Cape and this was attributed to capture myopathy (Van Rooyen⁵, pers. comm. 2020). All the other jackals that were captured and released using both techniques survived for at least six weeks post-capture.

The helicopter capture cost ZAR 5,800 (US\$ 307.86) per hour of flying time. In addition, there was an extra charge of ZAR 300 (US\$ 15.92) per captured jackal due to the nets being damaged through chewing, resulting in a total cost of ZAR 23,500 (US\$ 1,247.35) and ZAR 131,200 (US\$ 6,963.91) for the Free State and Eastern Cape areas, respectively. The cost equated to ZAR 11,900 (US\$ 631.63) per collared jackal. In contrast, the total cost associated with the employment of a professional trapper (including all equipment and travel costs) was ZAR 120,000 – a cost of ZAR 40,000 (US\$ 2,123.14) per collared jackal.

DISCUSSION

In this article we have demonstrated, for the first time, that helicopter net-gunning is an effective and safe technique for capturing jackals. From a research perspective, a method was required to capture multiple jackals in a short timeframe to facilitate the analysis of intraspecific spatial, temporal, and social dynamics. We successfully captured and released 13 jackals in total, one in the Free State and nine unique individuals in the Eastern Cape, as two of them were separate recaptures. The combined capture success rate for both areas, 0.5 jackals or 0.4 unique jackals per hour of flight, was comparable to other helicopter net-gunning studies of a similar species, coyote (0.40 per flight hour; Nelson *et al.* 2006). The capture success rate for padded leghold traps was similar to that of another jackal study in a farmland area, at a rate of 0.6 jackals per 100 trap-days (Botha *et al.* 2022). In our case, if we had only used the padded leghold traps, it would not have been possible to capture an adequate number

of jackals within the time allocated to the study. Helicopter net-gunning is effective even where study sites comprise large, inaccessible areas. While flying, helicopters can traverse large territories in a short period of time and allow for the capture of animals in areas that may not be accessible or practical using other capture methods. Although some jackals that we attempted to net-gun escaped into natural dens or burrows, the shrubland habitat did not hinder the effective use of helicopter net-gun capture as, once located, jackals could quickly be followed and manoeuvred into areas suitable for netting. Furthermore, using this proactive and focussed approach allows for the capture of multiple individuals on the same day. This additional benefit, from a research implementation perspective, reduces the cost of having an on-call veterinarian on standby and potentially reduces the travel costs as a result of unpredictable capture rates.

The relatively low capture success rate was likely a consequence of the time of year when the helicopter capture was attempted (August is when jackal pups are born in the Free State area (Deacon 2010), possibly explaining why three of the four jackals observed early in the morning were sitting at what appeared to be dens, where they disappeared immediately at the helicopter's approach). The mortality of the jackal that was captured in the Free State was likely attributable to the novelty of the technique and inexperience of the crew during this first capture session. In wildlife capture, mortalities are more common during the initial stages of operations, when procedures for capturing individuals have not been optimised for a specific species or environment (Armeno *et al.* 2006; Hampton *et al.* 2020). As far as we know, ours is the first attempt at net-gunning jackals from a helicopter for research purposes in South Africa. As a result, our initially unrefined methodology and inexperience may have compromised early capture attempts. During the initial implementation, it was advised to sedate netted individuals at the capture site before loading them into the helicopter, aiming to minimize stress and the risk of harm to both the jackals and personnel during transportation to the ground team. However, this approach resulted in the mortality of the captured jackal within a day of release. Fortunately, this allowed for a full post-mortem to be conducted to ascertain the cause of the death.

After discussion of the post-mortem observations with several veterinarians, it was concluded that a

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variety of factors contributed to the mortality of the netted individual. Administering the anaesthetic at the point of capture likely impaired the thermoregulatory mechanisms. That, in conjunction with dehydration and elevated heat production, stress hormones and elevated heart rate after being chased may have increased the mortality risk (Di Concetto *et al.* 2004). Minimising stress when handling wild animals is crucial to ensure their physiological health as prolonged stress can result in capture myopathy (Paterson 2014). Therefore, it is essential to limit the number of personnel involved in handling the captured (and immobilised) animals, and to maintain a quiet and calm working environment in their proximity. The captured animals must be allowed to recover from any sedation or anaesthesia at a safe distance (>50 m) away from human disturbances, especially in regions where they are heavily persecuted. Based on the outcome of the post-mortem of the jackal captured in the Free State and the resultant veterinary advice (Strauss, pers. comm.), the animal handling protocols were modified. Rather than anaesthetising the jackals immediately upon capture, anaesthetics and sedatives were only administered once the animal had had time to calm down and cool down in the confines of a recovery cage. This approach helped to reduce stress and lower the time of sustained human handling for the captured jackals.

Despite helicopter net-gunning maintaining a low risk of mortality when capturing wildlife, there remain concerns about the possibility of lethal and sub-lethal effects (Gese *et al.* 1987; Nelson *et al.* 2006). Mortality may occur directly from physical trauma, or indirectly, due to capture-induced stress (Barret *et al.* 1982). For example, jackals may be impacted directly by the weights that are attached to the capture net, when fired. The animal may also get injured from falling when netted from a helicopter (Webb *et al.* 2008). Indirectly, animals may succumb to capture myopathy from the stress of capture, handling and immobilisation, which may manifest even days or weeks after capture (Barret *et al.* 1982). Animals may also be vulnerable to post-capture stress, ataxia and disorientation after release, increasing the likelihood of predation or accidents (Di Concetto *et al.* 2004). During the post-anaesthesia recovery from sedation, a potential threat of predation also. Therefore, it is recommended that the animal be transferred to a holding cage to allow for full recovery before its release.

Helicopter net-gunning does not inherently require chemical immobilisation. Anaesthetic drugs can influence the heart and respiration rates, and decrease the ability to thermoregulate, providing an additional risk to the captured animal (DelGiudice *et al.* 2005; Larsen & Kreegar 2007). Manual restraint techniques have been developed and applied effectively to

canids, specifically *Lupulella adustus* and *Lupulella mesomelas* in the Serengeti region of East Africa (Craft 2007). The development of manual restraint techniques for jackals followed leghold captures in a distinct context. Furthermore, the jackals in the Craft (2007) study were not exposed to the same degree of human persecution as those in the current study areas. Manual restraint obviates the expenses, risks and logistical constraints associated with chemical immobilisation. Previous research on chemical immobilisation of jackals has shown that the time from administering anaesthesia to release ranges from 48 to 140 minutes, excluding the time spent in the trap prior to handling (Kaunda 2001; Admasu *et al.* 2004; Di Concetto *et al.* 2004). Physical handling techniques (without chemical sedation) used by Craft (2007) in relatively open and flat terrain, next to a water hole and inside a conservation area, resulted in the successful capture and release of jackals quickly and efficiently, potentially lowering stress levels and the risk of capture myopathy. However, it is recommended that researchers consider the various risks and limitations in their specific study area before proceeding, as chemical immobilisation may be required in some circumstances (Latham *et al.* 2020).

The time and financial implications of capturing animals need to be considered when designing spatial ecology studies. Our study compared the costs of two trapping methods for capturing jackals within the same study areas. Surprisingly (as helicopter hourly rates are relatively high), it turned out that helicopter capture was the more cost-effective capture technique in our circumstances. The net-gun approach resulted in a ZAR 11,900 (US\$ 631.63) cost per collared animal. For comparison, a ground-based effort in the same area over three weeks, with leghold traps, resulted in a 3.4 times higher cost of ZAR 40,000 or US\$ 2,123.14 per collared animal. Studies on some other species have also indicated that helicopter net-gunning can be the cheapest and most efficient approach (Jessup *et al.* 1988; Desert Bighorn Sheep *Ovis canadensis nelsoni*). Here, the lower cost was also realised through reduced personnel and a higher daily capture rate. Leghold trapping requires a substantial daily effort of checking and maintaining all the traps. Furthermore, there is a risk of capturing non-target species in leghold traps which may result in injuries, mortalities and predation on the captured animal; risks that are obviated by net-gunning. We conclude by stating that the ground-based approach would have been more expensive, more time-consuming, ethically less acceptable and, from a scientific point of view, less favourable than aerial net-gunning (it takes longer to catch the desired number of study animals).

We recommend that helicopter net-gunning be considered for the capture of jackals in large study areas,

especially in anthropogenically altered habitats where jackals are actively persecuted. Wildlife capture methods should be carefully selected based on their effectiveness, safety, cost, research design, and risk to target and non-target animals. However, further research is required on capture stress and post-capture movements to determine the extent of any long-term effects that this capture technique may have on jackals. This technique does, however, include risks to both jackals and humans not present in other methods (e.g. a helicopter crash). The ability to effectively capture multiple individuals within a short period, and to target critical research needs, is a major advancement over alternative methods (cage trapping and foothold trapping). The broader application of net-gunning would allow for a greater understanding of jackal ecology in South Africa and, therefore, also contribute to the development of more sustainable management methods. Further refinements to this capture method could be achieved by scheduling capture efforts for the most appropriate season. For example, one can expect to catch a relatively large percentage of young individuals during the dispersing months (February to April in central South Africa), while capture success may be relatively low during the pupping months (August to September) (Deacon 2010). Furthermore, documenting the circumstances under which the capture attempts were conducted, the post-capture condition and activity of the animals (both while captive and subsequent to release), can help establish best practices for this method (Hampton *et al.* 2020).

We aimed to determine whether a helicopter net-gun approach for jackal capture was feasible and to compare it with already established capture techniques. Our study was not designed to indicate the best capture season, or to assess whether there was an optimal time of the day for the capture of jackals. However, as a point of departure we recommend only to attempt captures early in the morning and late in the afternoon, and limit chase time to a maximum of 10 minutes. It was apparent that jackals were usually sighted within the first hour of the helicopter arriving in the search area. Prolonged searches may reduce the cost effectiveness of this approach as jackals probably retreat into culverts and dens; a potential consequence of the sustained hunting pressure in the area. Results of both the August and February sampling periods hint at the importance of timing capture attempts. During August (start of the whelping season in the Bethulie area; Deacon 2010) sampling, three of the four jackals sighted sat in the proximity of dens in the early morning and disappeared underground at the sight of the helicopter. During the February sampling period (early-dispersal period; Deacon 2010), a relatively high number of younger individuals were

captured. More information of this nature would be most useful as it can guide the scheduling of capture sessions based on the desired demographic of the study animals that are required. Bingham and Purchase (2002) have, for instance, made mention of the significant variation in the timing of the breeding season of jackals. Hall-Martin and Botha (1980) have inferred that, in some areas in the Eastern Cape, jackal pups are produced in the late spring and early summer. A higher incidence of capture of juveniles at this time may also be explained by curiosity where the younger individuals have not developed compensatory behaviours in response to persecution (Botha *et al.* 2022; Avenant pers. obs.).

Future investigations should also assess physiological indicators, including stress hormone concentrations, in individuals that undergo chemical immobilisation compared to those that are only subjected to physical restraint (*sensu* Craft 2007). Additionally, future research should evaluate the most favourable period for net-gunning by examining climatic, temporal and seasonal (related to mating, breeding and dispersal) factors, and assessing whether these correlate with increased or reduced capture success. Analysing fine scale jackal movement from satellite telemetry could reveal when animals are less likely to be near dens and refuges. This information might enhance the probability of successful capture (Green *et al.* 2021).

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